

Cupric Complexes of some Ortho-Hydroxy-Azo Dyes: Part III

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This paper deals with the synthesis and study of a number of substituted ortho-hydroxy azo dyes and a study of their cupric complexes. The highest complex formed is ML_2 as determined conductometrically and confirmed spectrophotometrically. The stability constants have been determined by Janssen's method with suitable modifications. The nitro dyes follow the reported order viz., $o > m > p$, but the chloro dyes exhibit the order $o > p > m$. A probable explanation for the apparent abnormal behaviour has been proposed.

In continuation of our previous work¹ the acid dissociation constants of several substituted (nitro-, chloro- and methyl)-6-hydroxy-azobenzene-3-sulphonic acid and the formation constants of their cupric complexes have been determined with a view to study the effect of these substituents in different positions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of the ligands: *p*-Sulphophenol was prepared¹ by the hydrolysis of diazotised sulphanilic acid (A.R.) To get the nitro dyes, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitro-anilines (B.D.H.) were diazotised in acid medium and the diazonium salts obtained were coupled with *p*-sulphophenol in alkaline medium. The dyes were recrystallised from 60% alcohol and dried at 110°. The chloro dyes were prepared similarly using chloroanilines (B.D.H.) in place of the nitroanilines. To get the methyl dyes, methylanilines (B.D.H.) were used. Freshly distilled *p*-methylaniline was diazotised and coupled with *p*-sulphophenol. The dye was repeatedly recrystallised from 80% alcohol and then dried. Attempts to get isomeric dyes with *o*- and *m*-toluidines resulted in highly resinous products, the results of analysis of which were rather disappointing and hence these were discarded.

The unsubstituted dye, 6-hydroxy-azobenzene-3-sulphonic acid (abbreviated to 3-sulpho dye), is the parent dye of this series. Its preparation was rather difficult, probably because aniline diazonium compound is a poorer coupler compared to nitro- and chloro-aniline diazonium compounds (containing these electro-negative groups). Electron-repelling groups like methyl should, therefore, decrease the positive charge on the diazonium nitrogen and hence toluidines should be poorer couplers. This is shown by the fact that although the dye with *p*-toluidine could be prepared with great difficulty, no dye could be prepared in pure state from *m*- and *o*-toluidines. The parent dye contained comparatively more of resinous product and hence 90% alcohol had to be used for its crystallisation and larger number of crystallisations became necessary for its purification. The result was a poorer yield. Results of analysis of the different dyes are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Dye Further substitution	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		% Chlorine	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Nil	9.31	9.33	10.62	10.62	—	—
2'-nitro	12.13	12.17	9.23	9.28	—	—
3'-nitro	12.13	12.17	9.24	9.28	—	—
4'-nitro	12.15	12.17	9.22	9.28	—	—
2'-chloro	8.32	8.37	9.51	9.54	10.62	10.61
3'-chloro	8.34	8.37	9.50	9.54	10.60	10.61
4'-chloro	8.33	8.37	9.51	9.54	10.58	10.61
4'-methyl	8.90	8.92	10.10	10.19	—	—

Study of the properties of the ligands and their cupric complexes : The pK_a values and the molar extinction coefficients of the ligands, the composition of the cupric complexes (ML_2) and the stability constants of the complexes were determined as in our previous communication¹. The molar extinction coefficient and pK_a values of the 3-sulpho dye (unsubstituted dye), 2'-nitro dye, 3'-nitro dye, 4'-nitro dye, 2'-chloro dye, 3'-chloro dye, 4'-chloro dye and 4'-methyl dye were determined at 426 $m\mu$, 452 $m\mu$, 466 $m\mu$, 488 $m\mu$, 450 $m\mu$, 456 $m\mu$, and 446 $m\mu$, respectively. While determining the stability constants of their cupric complexes, the pH of the mixtures was kept about one unit lower than their pK_a values since at higher pH values Cu^{++} gets precipitated. The wavelengths used for this were 500 $m\mu$ and 400 $m\mu$, 500 $m\mu$, 460 $m\mu$, 480 $m\mu$, 380 $m\mu$, 350 $m\mu$, 360 $m\mu$, and 480 $m\mu$, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pK_a values, of the ligands and $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ values of their cupric complexes are given in table II.

TABLE II

Dye Further substitution	pK_a	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Nil	7.53	6.08	4.42	10.50
2'-nitro	7.43	6.01	4.35	10.36
3'-nitro	7.15	6.02	4.38	10.40
4'-nitro	7.12	5.99	4.39	10.38
2'-chloro	7.83	6.07	4.45	10.52
3'-chloro	7.51	6.04	4.42	10.46
4'-chloro	7.55	6.03	4.40	10.43
4'-methyl	7.72	6.07	4.43	10.50

The group effect on the pK_a values of the ligands and on the stability constants of the complexes is clearly marked if the substituent is present in the phenol ring. In the present paper only those ligands have been taken which contain the same group (sulpho) in position 3. Naturally if the substituent is present on the amine side its effect will be but smaller. This is clearly seen from table II. However, the effect is still discernible although comparatively small. Electron-repelling methyl group increases pK_a value. That is why pK_a of 4'-methyl dye is larger (7.72) than that of the unsubstituted 3-sulpho dye (7.53). Electron-attracting nitro group should naturally lower the pK_a value and this has been observed (from 7.53 to 7.15 in the case of 3'-nitro dye). Because of the peculiar character of the chloro group its effect on the pK_a value is either unexpected rise (*o*-chloro 7.83) or slight rise (*p*-chloro, 7.55) or even slight fall (*m*-chloro, 7.51).

Coming to the position effects of these groups, as already stated, there is not enough data for the methyl group. Moreover, these effects are of a considerably smaller order. For the nitro and the chloro groups, although necessary data has been collected, the differences are rather small. Hence too much emphasis cannot be laid. The effect of nitro group in the 3' and 4' positions, of the chloro group in 2' and 3' positions and of the methyl in the 4' position is only significant. For the nitro group, the general trend is that the pK_a lowering effect goes on increasing in order 2'(ortho), 3'(meta) and 4'(para), although the difference between positions 3' and 4' is nominal. This observation is in accordance with that of Kido². The pK_a of 2'-nitro is rather higher (7.43). This is probably because of the possibility of hydrogen bond formation. In the case of the chloro dyes the order of decreasing pK_a is ortho > para > meta. These differences between the pK_a values of 3'-chloro and 4'-chloro is again nominal. This can be explained on the basis that the chloro group is a σ -acceptor but a π -donor. From the position 3'(meta) the π -effect cannot be felt but the σ -acceptor character has some effect so that 3'-chloro group lowers the pK_a somewhat. From the position 2'(ortho) the σ -acceptor character would be felt to a greater extent but the π -donor character of the chloro group becomes now much more effective and hence the pK_a is sufficiently raised (from 7.53 to 7.83). 4'-Chloro (para) is again less effective, since π -effect can be transmitted from the para position. Naturally, the effect is now much less due to increasing distance from the ring A (phenol ring). These observations do not fall in line with the observation of Kido (*loc.cit*) because the pK_a of the para is more than that of the meta compound. This is because the opposed π -effect does not operate from the meta position.

A close relationship is well expected between ligand basicity and complex stability. Calvin and Wilson³ and Fernalius *et al.*⁴ have shown that the linear plots of pK_a and $\log K_1$ or $\log \beta_2$ are only rough and are obtained only for structurally very closely related ligands, which form π -bonds to much the same extent. When a large number of different ligands are studied the correlation requires the use of different straight lines. These have been explained by pointing out that a metal ion like Cu(II) takes part in the resonance of the chelate

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ring³, by dative d_{π} bonding by the Cu(II) ion⁵. Thus, extension of the conjugation has relatively lesser effect on σ -electron density at the site of coordination, but it markedly lowers the π -electron density and then allows much stable coordination with π -donor Cu(II). The 3-sulpho dyes studied show slightly higher stability probably because from the para position 3 the acceptor sulpho group can better promote the π -bonding with d_{π} donor Cu(II).

The values of $\log K_2$ would naturally be much less than for $\log K_1$. In the value of $\log K_2$ the electrostatic effect is so small due to the charge in the central ion reaching practically to zero, it is obvious that the "rest effect" becomes comparatively much more important. Hence the linear correlations can no longer be expected in accordance with observations of Jillot and Williams⁶ and Basolo and Murmann⁷. In accordance with these observations, in the present work also, no direct relation between pK_a and $\log K_2$ can be drawn. That also explains why no linear correlation can be drawn between pK_a and $\log \beta_2$, since β_2 is a composite constant being equal to $(K_1 \cdot K_2)$.

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